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Teachers Classroom Management and Disciplinary Practices Towards Learners' Behavior

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Abstract

This study examined the classroom management and disciplinary practices towards the learner's behavior of the teacher for the school year 2023-2024. The research focused on 130 teachers from Nunungan District and selected schools from Sultan Naga Dimaporo District. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study aimed to identify the teachers' practices in terms of classroom management styles and disciplinary practices toward learners' behavior within the specific population during the first semester of the specified school year. The findings revealed that the teachers predominantly adopted an authoritative management style, emphasizing a genuine concern for learners' learning experiences. The study came to the conclusion that common misbehaviors were commonplace, including fighting, disruptive behavior, and attention-seeking. Occasionally, peer pressure, personal issues, and attention-seeking were the causes of misbehavior. Furthermore, only some facets of classroom management—like thorough planning and encouraging an honest conversation with students—showed a noteworthy favorable impact on students' behavior. Teachers had to prepare their classrooms because it had a good correlation with students' behavior. The respondents' age significantly influenced their classroom management style, and their civil status was found to be a key determinant of classroom management techniques. Being married had something to do with the respondent's classroom management because married respondent had their own experiences with managing their own children at home. Length of service had a significant effect on the classroom management style. It was often considered an important factor in determining a teacher's experience and expertise in classroom management.

Keywords: *classroom management, disciplinary practices, learner's behavior, teaching styles, learner's well-being*

Introduction

Classroom management and practices of teachers are some of the factors that contribute to the behavior of learners during the teaching and learning process. Ineffective classroom management and practices often result in disruptive behavior of learners. It also manifests less academic engagement which leads to low academic performance. On the other hand, it is observed that teachers who manage the classroom properly create a conducive atmosphere for learning and participative learners.

In the classroom, students engage with one another with the shared goal of imparting and receiving knowledge. Classroom procedures need to be inclusive for them to be effectively communicated, making sure that each student feels respected and encouraged to pursue their education. Moreover, classroom management refers to the collection of protocols, tactics, and teaching techniques that educators employ to establish a learning-oriented atmosphere in the classroom. In order to teach and study in a secure and organized setting that supports inclusion and high-quality education, classroom management is crucial. The way students behave with their teachers and peers is another aspect of classroom practices. The ideal conditions for learning must be provided in the classroom. They ought to feel as though they have the same opportunities to learn as other students in the classroom. As a result, in addition to the classroom environment, the sort of pedagogy the teacher employs during the teaching process has a significant impact on the learning results of the students.

In addition, educators have a pivotal role in overseeing classroom procedures and ought to be focused on modifying their teaching methods. The teacher-learner performance relationship is complex, as evidenced by the teacher/class/context impact, but the teacher plays a vital role in effective education. This is because a consistent context-related teacher management system is required by some elements (Best, Tournier, & Chimier, 2018).

Classroom management is the process by which teachers and schools create and maintain appropriate behavior of learners in classroom settings. Moreover, classroom management is essential in teaching because it is the way how teacher manages her learners to be motivated in learning and be active inside the classroom. As observed by the researcher, several learners were not listening to the teacher during discussion, not participating in the given activities, and were always absent. As a result, this is due to the teachers' negligence in providing a conducive learning environment for the learners and to provide motivation.

The basic factor that gives meaningful and effective learning is the ability of the teacher to control the classroom environment. Classroom management is important because it influences learners' achievement. It helps learners develop responsibility and self-regulation to avoid unnecessary disruption in studying. Indeed, one of the most important roles of the teacher is to manage the classroom well. A teacher's approach to managing the classroom is a major factor in inspiring students. Additionally, it offers a supportive learning atmosphere where students can develop their physical, mental, and spiritual well-being.

Furthermore, it is common knowledge that the first skill a teacher needs to master to provide the greatest, most efficient instruction is classroom management. Regarding curricular instruction and student safety, all teachers are expected to meet the same standards.

Educators employ varying approaches to achieve these benchmarks, nevertheless (McAdoo, 2021).

It is stated that teachers are vital in helping schools deliver quality education through the effective and efficient utilization of classroom management and discipline. The main goal of a classroom teacher's job is to create the best learning environment possible. Because of this, teaching is a dynamic profession that is impacted by many different elements, such as student and teacher traits, relationships between schools and the community, and educational resources. The interpersonal contact between the teacher and the student is widely recognized as being essential to the teaching and learning process, even if all of these elements play a role in creating a healthy learning environment (Obispo et al., 2021).

Lack of learners' discipline is one of the biggest problems that public school teachers are facing nowadays. Teachers have spent a large portion of time and effort on how they can improve the behaviors of learners and the causes of those behaviors. Each year, a teacher's classroom has different behaviors from the previous years which means that their routines and the way they teach different strategies may be changed. The overall goal of any teacher and any school is to support a learner academically, socially, and emotionally (Kirkpatrick, 2019). This is why a teacher needs to be proactive in adapting their approach and remain flexible as they explore the best fit for their classes. The effectiveness of teachers in classroom management strategies can determine the overall success of the school year.

These policies are hereby understood to include the State's obligation to teach students appropriately about school discipline, their obligations to their peers, their teachers and other authority figures, and community members, as stated in House Bill No. 5735 Section 2. To do this, the State must institutionalize policies that establish explicit guidelines for acceptable student conduct toward other students, instructors, and staff, as well as during class and outside of school grounds, in all public schools.

Given the above information, the researcher has felt the urgency to conduct this study and to examine and ascertain the classroom management and practices of teachers in Nunungan District and teachers in selected schools of Sultan Naga Dimaporo District Lanao del Norte Division. The study sought to find out the respondents' classroom management style and disciplinary practices toward learners' behavior during the school year 2023-2024. As a resident and a teacher in Nunungan District Lanao del Norte Division, the researcher is credible to conduct this study for the improvement of her service and for the benefit of the teachers and school to which she is currently assigned.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the classroom practices in terms of classroom management styles and disciplinary practices of the respondents in relation to the level of learners' behavior. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of;
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 plantilla position; and
 - 1.5 length of service?
2. What is the level classroom management of the respondents in terms of;
 - 2.1 authoritative style;
 - 2.2 authoritarian style;
 - 2.3 permissive style; and
 - 2.4 indulgent style?
3. What is the level of learners' behavior in the classroom and some possible reasons for doing so?
4. What are the reasons for learners' classroom misbehavior?
5. What is the extent of respondents' disciplinary practices towards learners' misbehavior?
6. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' management styles and learners' behavior?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and classroom management style?
8. What action plan for classroom management can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods that were employed in this study. Specifically, it contains discussions on the research design, research environment, respondents of the study, sampling procedures, research instruments, their reliability and validity, and statistical treatment that was used in analyzing and interpreting data.

Research Design

This study gathered and analyzed data pertinent to the statement of the problem using the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive-correlational study attempted to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more variables. It is descriptive in the sense that the respondents were described according to their profile in terms of age, civil status, highest

educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service, and the classroom practices of the teacher towards learners' behavior. Likewise, the extent of the classroom management style of the respondents was discussed as well as the learners' classroom misbehavior, reasons for misbehaving, and the respondents' disciplinary practices towards learners' misbehavior.

On the other hand, correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between teachers' management styles and learners' behavior and the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and classroom management style.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the teachers of Nunungan District, and Sultan Naga Dimaporo District Division of Lanao del Norte. These teachers are from Nunungan Central Elementary School, Dimayon Elementary School, Kaludan Elementary School, Carcum Elementary School, Lupitan Elementary School, Masibay Integrated School, Nunungan National high school, Rebucon Primary School, Bangco Primary School, Inayawan Primary School, Liangan Primary School, Mangan Primary School, Katubuan Primary School, Rarab Primary School, Pantar Primary School, and Taraka Primary School.

Moreover, the selected Sultan Naga Dimaporo District schools are the following: Koreo Elementary School, Bangaan Elementary School, Calibao Elementary School, Piraka Elementary school, Dableston Elementary School, Sultan Naga Dimaporo South Central School, Sultan Naga Dimaporo West Central School, Mamagum Elementary School, Kirapan Elementary School, Khalid B. Bantasan Elementary School, Sultan Ali Dimaporo Memorial Integrated School, Sultan Naga Dimaporo Integrated School and Payong Primary School. Fifty percent (50%) of the teacher population from all the schools mentioned were taken as respondents of the total of 130 teachers' respondents as shown in Table 1 using the fish ball technique. There were 130 teachers taken randomly as respondents of this study for the school year 2023-2024.

Table 1. *Distribution of Nunungan and Sultan Naga Dimaporo District Respondents*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>Number of Teachers</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
A. Nunungan District		
Nunungan Central Elementary School	10	5
Dimayon Elementary School	4	2
Kaludan Elementary School	6	3
Carcum Elementary School	6	3
Lupitan Elementary School	4	2
Masibay Integrated School	18	9
Nunungan National High School	5	2
Rebucon Primary School	3	2
Bangco Primary School	3	2
Inayawan Primary School	1	1
Liangan Primary School	1	0
Mangan Primary School	2	1
Katubuan Primary School	3	1
Rarab Primary School	2	1
Pantar Primary School	2	1
Taraka Primary School	2	1
B. Sultan Naga Dimaporo District		
Koreo Elementary School	9	5
Bangaan Elementary School	10	5
Calibao Elementary School	10	5
Piraka Elementary School	9	4
Dableston Elementary School	24	12
Sultan Naga Dimaporo South Central School	26	13
Sultan Naga Dimaporo West Central School	8	4
Mamagum Elementary School	8	4
Kirapan Elementary School	7	3
Khalid B. Bantasan Elementary School	36	18
Sultan Ali Dimaporo Memorial Integrated School	29	15
Sultan Naga Dimaporo Integrated School	4	2
Payong Primary School		
Total	260	130

Instruments

This study utilized a questionnaire adapted from Joseph F. McGinty (2000). Before the questionnaire was finalized, this was submitted to the adviser for suggestions and comments. After, it underwent content validation through pilot testing to the 25 teachers in Sapad District, Division of Lanao del Norte who were not respondents of the study. The reliability coefficient was 0.81 which was an assurance that the instrument was reliable.

The parts of the questionnaire that were modified were first the teacher's classroom management styles, the researcher reshuffled the questions of the different teaching styles, and modified some of the questions to make them shorter by changing some difficult words into much simpler ones. In addition, part III of the questionnaire about the learner's behavior was modified by omitting some of the questions and selecting only the researcher-observed possible behavior of the learners in the classroom.

The classroom management questions were given to each respondent. Its purpose was to determine a teacher's style of classroom management. Answers were evaluated by using the 4-Likert scale from 4 (always), 3 (often), 2 (sometimes) and 1 (never). The score was then added according to its category test items numbers 2, 7, 9, 14, and 17 to determine the teacher's score for authoritative style, responses from statement 1, 8, 12, 15, and 16 to determine the teacher's score for authoritarian style, responses from statement 4, 5, 11, 19, and 20 to determine the teacher's score for permissive style, and responses from statement 3, 6, 10, 13 and 18 to determine the teacher's score for indulgence style. The learner's behavior scores in letters a, b, and c were evaluated by adding the numerical responses of the respondents.

The questionnaire was composed of three parts. The first part was about the demographic profile of the respondents which answered their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, and length of service. The second part of the questionnaire was the teacher's classroom management style which was either authoritative style, authoritarian style, permissive style, or indulgence style. The third part of the questionnaire was the learner's behavior, which was composed of learners' classroom misbehavior, reasons for learners' classroom misbehavior, and respondents' disciplinary practices.

Procedure

The following was the process of gathering the data. The researcher asked permission from the Dean of Graduate Studies and the consent of the adviser to distribute the questionnaire. A letter was signed by the Dean and the Adviser. Then the researcher personally visited the public elementary schools of Nunungan District and selected schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo District, Division of Lanao del Norte covered in the study to administer and retrieve the questionnaire. To facilitate the gathering of the data permissions to conduct the study were obtained from the schools' division superintendent, supervisor, principals, and school heads. All the communications were signed and approved by the concerned personalities.

The study was conducted at Nunungan District and selected schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo District Division of Lanao del Norte, the researcher floated the questionnaire on the first semester of school year 2023-2024, it was distributed first to Nunungan District teachers through a fish ball technique. The respondents had to pick the questionnaire from the box and those who picked up a blank sheet of paper were not going to answer the questionnaire. The same process was done when floating the questionnaire to selected schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo District.

During the distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher further explained the importance and mechanics of how to answer some parts of it. Confidentiality of their answers was also assured by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented. Problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used to describe the respondents' demographic profile in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, and length of service. Problems 2, 3, 4, and 5 Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe the classroom practices of the teachers in terms of classroom management styles and the level of learners' behavior. Problems 6 and 7 Regression analysis was used in determining the significant relationship between teachers' management styles and learners' behavior and between the respondents' demographic profile and classroom management style.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that are shown in the tables. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, and length of service?

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

<i>Age Bracket (yrs. Old)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26-30	42	32.00%
31-35	44	34.00%
36-40	34	26.00%
41 and above	10	8.00%
Total	130	100.00

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. It showed that the highest number was coming from the age bracket between 31 and 35 years old which was 44 or 34% out of the 130 respondents. While the least number of respondents were from the

age bracket of 41 and above years of age which was only 10 or 8%. As could be gleaned from the results, the respondents were widely dispersed in terms of their ages although a significant number of them were much younger than their colleagues with educators ranging from those who had just entered the profession to those who had been teaching for several decades. It was common for a mix of young and experienced teachers to be present in the education system.

As cited in the study of Bungai and Perdana (2018) younger teachers usually cultivated learners' curiosity and interest in learning. Teachers recognized and tried to fulfill their responsibilities to their learners.

Table 3. Respondents' Civil Status

<i>Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single	34	26.00%
Married	91	70.00%
Separated	5	4.00%
Total	130	100.00

Table 3 shows the respondent's profile in terms of civil status. It could be gleaned that the majority of the respondents were married which was 91 out of 130 or 70%. While 26% or 34 of the respondents were single and 5 or 4% were separated from their spouses. It was indicated in the results that 70% of the respondents had a family of their own since they were married. This meant that besides teaching there were other responsibilities teachers should attend like the provision of the needs of family members.

According to Glantz and Krueger (2023), marriages that took place when the couple was in their late 20s to mid-30s were most successful. By the time they got to their late 20s, they had a clear sense of who they were and what they wanted out of life. They added that once they got to this age, they were more established, more settled, and were more focused. Additionally, by the time one had reached their late 20s or mid-30s, generally, they were aware, experienced, and mature when it comes to dealing with trauma, issues such as emotional, health, financial, etc., and communication.

On the other hand, the Philippines does not have a divorce law. In the Philippines, the predominant legal framework for ending a marriage was through annulment or legal separation. Annulment was a legal procedure that declared a marriage null and void. Legal separation, on the other hand, allowed spouses to live separately without dissolving the marriage. Additionally, the absence of divorce in the Philippines was largely influenced by cultural, religious, and historical factors. It had played a significant role in shaping family law in the Philippines (Abalos, 2017).

Table 4. Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor's Degree	73	56.00%
Bachelor's Degree with MA units	44	34.00%
Master's Degree	13	10.00%
Total	130	100.00

Table 4 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their highest educational attainment. Majority were bachelor's Degree holders which were 73 out of 130 respondents or 56%. Forty-four teacher respondents had masteral units while only 13 or 10% were master's degree holders. These findings were clear indication that respondents needed upgrading them professionally. Additionally, the results indicated that teachers in Nunungan district and selected schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo district were in need of professional development. The Commission on Higher Education in the Philippines required teachers at higher education level to have at least a master's degree related to the field in which they teach.

According to Olmedo and Fernández (2018), that the basic purpose of the professional competencies of educators was to prepare the administrators for the host of internal and external demands that would affect the school and teacher competency. These would enhance learners' achievement. Additionally, educational attainment could contribute to the quality of instruction in the classroom. Teachers with advanced degrees may be better equipped to design effective lesson plans, assess learner learning, and address individual learner needs. Teachers with higher levels of education could positively impact learner outcomes, including academic achievement and future educational attainment.

Table 5. Respondents' Plantilla Position

<i>Plantilla Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
T I	98	75.00%
T II	17	13.00%
T III	11	9.00%
Master Teacher I	4	3.00%
Total	130	100.00

From the presentation of table 5, it showed that 75% or 98 out of 130 respondents were holding the plantilla position of Teacher I. While the least number of respondents were the Master Teachers which was only 4 out of 130 or 3%. The findings revealed that

Nunungan District and selected schools in Sultan Naga Dimaporo were lacking of Master Teachers. Prior to being granted tenure, teachers were extensively assessed, heavily mentored, and carefully chosen when they first entered the teaching profession. This made sure that those who wanted to become teachers at the professional level could do so by meeting a competency requirement, which allowed them to advance their knowledge over the course of their careers (Kini & Podolsky, 2018).

In addition, based on MEC Order No.10, s. 1979, the number of Master Teacher 1 positions allotted to each district may be estimated by multiplying the number of teachers in the district by .05, the number of teachers in a district remained the same but those appointed Master Teacher only got augmentation in pay retaining their usual items. Master teacher shall be selected based on the enclosed criteria. It was stressed that a candidate must possess all the qualifications specified, unless otherwise indicated, no substitution for the qualifications required shall be allowed.

Table 6. Respondents' Length of Service

Years	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	39	30.00%
6-10 years	58	45.00%
11-15 years	24	18.00%
16 and above years	9	7.00%
Total	130	100.00

Table 6 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their length of service. It revealed that the highest number were those who served for 6-10 years in the Department of Education whose frequency was 58 out of 130 or 45%. Followed by 39 respondents or 30% who served for about 1-5 years. The least number of respondents were those who had 16 and above years in the service which was 9 or only 7% out of the total 100%. This implied that most of the respondents were new and also based on Table 2 results 34% or 44 out of 130 respondents were aged 31-35 followed by 32% or 42 respondents fell in the age bracket of 26-30 which connoted that their year of service was still limited.

Kini and Podolsky (2018) asserted that as educators accumulated experience, their efficacy as educators continued to grow. Overall, a teacher's professional achievement as a teacher was favorably correlated with their teaching experience. Of course, there were differences in the efficacy of teachers at all levels of their careers. Therefore, not all new teachers were generally less effective, and not all seasoned teachers were more successful.

Problem 2: What is the level of classroom management of the respondents in terms of authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and indulgent?

Table 7. Authoritative Classroom Management

Classroom Management Item statement	Weighted Mean	Remarks
CMS2. I am concerned about both what my learners learn and how they learn.	4.00	Always
CMS7. I always try to explain the reasons behind my rules and decisions.	3.67	Always
CMS9. My learners understand that they can interrupt my lecture if they have a relevant question.	3.49	Often
CMS14. I encourage my learners to freely "speak his/her mind", even if he/she disagrees with me.	3.58	Always
CMS 17. I respect my learner's opinion and encourage him/her to express them.	3.90	Always
Average	3.73	Always

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 7 displays the classroom management level of the respondents in terms of authoritative management style. The results revealed that the respondents always practice this kind of management style as evidenced by the average weighted mean of 3.73 among the five (5) authoritative management style items. The highest mean which all the respondents answered the highest score of four (4) was that the respondents were very concerned about what the learners learned and how they learned. The least weighted mean of 3.49 (often) was about the learners; understanding that they could interrupt the teachers' discussion if they have relevant inquiry. The findings further disclosed the respondents used an authoritative style in managing their learner's behavior.

This suggested that the instructor's employment of an authoritative style had a significant impact on the students' academic achievement. Moreover, it significantly affected the students' performance (Bacat, 2019). This further suggested that while encouraging independence, the teacher nevertheless imposed boundaries and constraints on the students. This instructor frequently gave explanations for the policies and choices made. The teacher would give a student who was misbehaving a harsh but polite reprimand. This teacher occasionally used punishment, but only after carefully evaluating the situation. Behavioral principles, high standards for proper behavior, explicit explanations of why particular acts were acceptable and others unacceptable, and friendly learner-teacher connections were its defining characteristics (Johnston, 2018). Teachers who supported and encouraged all of the learners in their classroom effectively, and who identified and targeted appropriate and desired behaviors with positive reinforcement, increased the likelihood of their being effective classroom behavior managers (Parsonson, 2020).

Table 8. *Authoritarian Classroom Management*

<i>Classroom Management Item statement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
CMS1. If a learner is disruptive during class, I assign him/her to detention, without further discussion.	1.51	Sometimes
CMS8. The classroom must be quiet in order for learners to learn.	3.29	Often
CMS.12 I will not accept excuses from a learner who is tardy.	3.49	Often
CMS15. I use criticism to make my learners improve his/her behavior.	1.82	Sometimes
CMS 16. I punish my learners by taking privileges away from them.	1.99	Sometimes
Average	2.01	Sometimes

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

As presented in Table 8, the authoritarian classroom management style obtained an average rating result of 2.01 weighted mean which implied that the respondents sometimes practice this kind of management style. Despite the high weighted mean of the classroom management statements 8 and 12 which were 3.29 and 3.49 respectively which meant the respondents often practiced these two, still the overall average weighted mean was low. It implied that teacher respondents often required the classroom to be quiet during classes and would not easily accept excuses when learners were late in coming to class. But they sometimes used criticism to make learners improved their behavior, punished their learners by taking privileges away from them, and if a learner was misbehaving, he/she would be assigned to detention without further discussion.

The findings further disclosed that the teacher had to use an authoritarian management style to discipline their learners sometimes. According to Parsonson (2020), teachers had to set the standards in their teaching for a better learning process as well as the behavior modification of the learners. Likewise, as cited by Chamundeswari (2019), supported that disciplinary problems in the class intervene with learning and disable the teacher from appropriately delivering lessons. In addition, strong and consistent classroom management with skill in controlling disciplinary problems had a significant impact on learner achievement. As a result, an orderly task-oriented approach to teaching and learning had the best effect on both the conduct and content management of the learner.

Table 9. *Permissive Classroom Management*

<i>Classroom Management Item statement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
CMS4. I don't want to reprimand a learner because it might hurt his/her feelings.	2.47	Sometimes
CMS5. The emotional well-being of my learners is more important than classroom control.	3.49	Often
CMS11. If a learner requests a hall pass, I always honor the request.	2.32	Sometimes
CMS19. I always put my learners' feelings first before mine.	3.49	Often
CMS 20. If a learner requests to play during class hours because they're bored, I always honor the request.	2.25	Sometimes
Average	2.80	Often

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 9 presents the weighted mean of the respondents' permissive classroom management style. The average weighted mean was 2.80 which fell under the description often. This implied that the respondents often considered the emotional well-being of the learners, and always put learners' feelings first before themselves. Also, respondents sometimes honored the request of the learner for a hall pass, and if the learners requested to play during class hours the respondents sometimes honored the request. This implied that the respondent just did not impose on the learners and placed only a few demands (Johnston, 2018). In addition, respondents did not place behavioral expectations on their learners, gave learners much freedom to express themselves, and made choices within the learning environment. Learners may feel more comfortable expressing their thoughts and feelings in such an environment. It was characterized by a lack of involvement and the environment was non-punitive. There were few demands on learners, and there was a lot of freedom. The learners in this class were left to do as they pleased, respondent did not impose rules for learners (McAdoo, 2021). On the contrary, a permissive classroom management style could create a positive and comfortable learning environment, but it may also present challenges. Some critics argued that without clear structure and expectations, learners might lack the guidance needed for optimal learning. Striking a balance between flexibility and structure was often key to effective classroom management. Teachers may need to adapt their management style based on the needs of individual learners and the dynamics of the classroom.

Table 10. *Indulgent Classroom Management*

<i>Classroom Management Item statement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
CMS3. I avoid imposing any rules on my learners.	2.46	Sometimes
CMS6. If a learner turns in a late homework assignment, it is not my problem.	1.62	Sometimes
CMS10. Class preparation isn't worth the effort.	1.24	Never
CMS13. I find it difficult to discipline my learners.	2.39	Sometimes
CMS 18. I ignore my learner's bad behavior.	1.59	Sometimes
Average	1.86	Sometimes

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 10 delves into the indulgent classroom management of the respondents in which the average weighted mean of 1.86 implied that teachers sometimes found it difficult to discipline learners, ignored learners' bad behavior, did not mind if learners had no assignments,

and did not impose classroom rules for the learners. On the other hand, respondents never assumed that classroom preparation was not worth their efforts. The results demonstrated that responders occasionally treat their students with an opulent management style. On occasion, they fostered disruptions or misconduct in the classroom. This was due to the respondent's genuine concern for the welfare of their students, which increased their level of involvement. Even so, they might occasionally come out as too amiable, which could undermine their power in the classroom. As a result, it was occasionally difficult to discipline students. Furthermore, respondents gave comfort and good relationships a higher priority than structure, regulations, and penalties (Noman, 2023).

Turanli (2018) revealed in his study that a well-organized and better-controlled learning environment contributed to learners' learning along with a warm climate. In terms of the relations between the teacher and the learners, too close relations may lead to learners' abuse of the teacher's attitude while too formal relations may decrease misbehavior and may also prevent interaction. When students became disinterested, the course plan was modified to keep them engaged.

Problem 3: What is the level of learners' misbehavior in the classroom and some possible reasons for doing so?

Table 11. *Learners' Classroom Misbehavior*

Misbehavior	Weighted Mean	Remarks
LBS1. Learners fighting during class discussion.	3.05	Often
LBS2. Name Calling of the classmates.	2.22	Sometimes
LBS3. Things being thrown around the room.	2.31	Sometimes
LBS4. Learners bothering other learners who are trying to work.	2.80	Often
LBS5. Learners who argue with the teacher.	1.65	Sometimes
LBS6. Noisy learners and un-participative.	2.73	Often
LBS7. Bullying of classmates.	3.07	Often
LBS8. Learners who take things that do not belong to them.	2.80	Often
LBS9. Pupils who are attention seeker	2.82	Often
Average	2.61	Often

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 11 shows the learners' level of misbehavior in the classroom. It could be gleaned that learners often fought during class discussions, bothered classmates who were working, were noisy and not participative in the discussion, bullied classmates, took things that were not their own and learners often sought attention from everyone. As evidenced by the average weighted mean of 2.61, these common misbehaviors of learners were often observable in the classroom. On the other hand, respondents sometimes experienced learners who argued with their respective teachers, threw some things inside the classroom, and did name-calling to their classmates. It had been determined that the behaviors that disrupted the motivation of the lesson and the teacher were disturbing the peace of the class by disturbing friends, speaking without permission, standing up without permission, trying to make friends talk during the lesson, trying to disrupt the lesson, and coming late to the class. In another subtheme, the tendency to violence came to the fore. This was explained as fighting with friends, making fun of friends, hitting a friend, and pushing a friend. Learners' misbehavior was rooted in the influence of complex factors inside and outside of schools (Kazak & Koyuncu, 2020). In addition, the finding entailed that classroom misbehavior among learners can be challenging for both teachers and learners. Poor behavior was a barrier to learning and could easily threaten the health and wellbeing of teachers. On top of other pressures that could occur, the result was lost teaching days, unhappy teachers and failing learners. Effectively managing learner behavior meant using a set of educational practices and strategies. Inappropriate behavior was prevented and efficiently managed, and an environment that supported both teaching and learning was established and maintained. Although these attitudes and actions may have started in childhood, they were later influenced by social influences that did not originate from the home, such as the types of instruction that students at all educational levels received (Johnston, 2018).

Problem 4: What are the reasons of learners' classroom misbehavior?

Table 12. *Reasons for Learners' Classroom Misbehavior*

Reasons	Weighted Mean	Remarks
RLBS1. Do not like the teacher	1.41	Never
RLBS2. Angry about something	2.55	Often
RLBS3. Get low scores on assessment	2.39	Sometimes
RLBS4. Hang around with others who misbehave	3.02	Often
RLBS5. Showing off in front of their peers	2.52	Often
RLBS6. Having problems at home	2.44	Sometimes
RLBS7. Don't like school	1.54	Sometimes
RLBS8. Don't like the assignments	1.83	Sometimes
RLBS9. Getting back at teacher	1.38	Never
Average	2.12	Sometimes

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 12 presents the level of learners' reasons to misbehave in the classroom. It revealed that often learners misbehave when they hang around with others who did the same, angry about something, and just to show off in front of their peers. Other reasons were

sometimes because of low scores in an assessment, having problems at home, did not like the school and assignments. On the other hand, respondents never assumed that learners did not like the teacher and getting back at them was the reason for their misbehavior inside the classroom. As evidenced by the average weighted mean of 2.12, these common reasons of learners for misbehaving were sometimes observed in the classroom. Some learners just wanted to walk into the classroom and they were not going to follow the norms of the classroom. They thought they heard them, yet disregarded directions. They created disruptions and prevented other learners from learning.

Learner misbehavior in the classrooms interrupted the smooth functioning of teaching learning process. A large number of factors were considered to be responsible for the learners' classroom misbehavior. Learner's lack of interest, lack of motivation, attention seeking, the classroom environment, teachers' attitude, the community and the family background of the learners were some of the factors mainly contributing to the reasons learners misbehave inside the classroom (Shamnadh & Anzari, 2019).

Problem 5: What is the extent of respondents' disciplinary practices towards learners' misbehavior?

Table 13. *Respondents' Disciplinary Practices*

<i>Practices</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
DPS1. Shouting at the learners who misbehave	1.44	Never
DPS2. Contacting the parents of misbehave learners.	3.65	Always
DPS3. Implementing reward system	3.36	Often
DPS4. Giving extra work to misbehave learners	2.28	Sometimes
DPS5. Keeping the learners in during recess time	1.47	Never
DPS6. Sending learners to another classroom	1.58	Sometimes
DPS7. Being sent to the guidance office/principal's office.	3.15	Often
DPS8. Providing motivating classroom activities	3.75	Always
DPS9. Providing effective instructional materials that can capture learners' attention	3.84	Always
Average	2.72	Often

Note: 1.00 --- 1.49 Never 2.50- 3.49 Often 1.50—2.49 Sometimes 3.50 - 4.00 Always

Table 13 presents the respondents disciplinary actions towards learners' misbehavior in the classroom. It showed that teachers always contacted the parents of learners who misbehaved, provided motivating classroom activities and also effective instructional materials that could capture learners' attention. It also revealed that teachers often implemented reward system and sent the learners who misbehave in the guidance office or in the principal's office. Other than that, the teachers sometimes gave extra work to those learners who were misbehaving and sent misbehaving learners to another classroom. On the other hand, teachers never shouted at the learners who misbehaved and never kept the learners in during recess time. The average weighted mean of the disciplinary practices of the respondents was 2.72 which fell under the description often.

Respondent always maintained open lines of communication with parents to discuss any behavioral concerns of the learners. They referred learners to school administrators who implemented more formal consequences. It was crucial for respondent to use a combination of these strategies based on the specific needs of their learners and the nature of the behaviors exhibited. The goal should be foster a positive and respectful learning environment that encouraged responsible behavior and personal growth.

According to Rahimi and Karkami (2015), the results of their study primarily showed that teachers generally use productive discipline strategies such as recognition/reward, involvement, discussion and motivation more than counterproductive strategies like aggression and punishment. This implied that respondents were perceived to be non-authoritarian, praised learners for good behavior and involved them in the process of discipline decision making. A caring teacher was the one who made the ground ready for learning tasks that needed genuine interaction, communication and cooperation among learners.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between teachers' management styles and learners' behavior?

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the teachers' management style and learners' behavior showed that out of the twenty (20) item statements only two (2) had significant relationship to learners' behavior. It implied that classroom preparation was a must for teachers since it positively correlated to the learner's behavior, likewise when teachers let the learners spoke freely even for disagreement from the teacher. This influenced the learners' behavior in a positive way. The rest of the items as shown in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance signified no correlation at all meaning whether teachers practiced these management statements, it had no effect on learners' behavior.

Class preparation, including how well teachers planned and organized their lessons, could have a significant impact on the behavior of learners. Well-prepared and engaging lessons captured learners' attention and interest. A well-prepared teacher was more likely to build positive relationships with learners. When learners felt that their teacher was organized, cared about their learning, and was committed to their success, they were more likely to exhibit positive behavior.

According to Pamela et al. (2018), teachers with stronger preparation in day-to-day issues were relatively more effective in teaching and teachers who had the opportunity in their preparation to engage in the actual practices involved in teaching also showed greater

learner gains. In addition, teacher preparation could make a difference in outcomes for learner. It focused more on the work of the classroom and provided opportunities for teachers to study what they would be doing produces teachers who were more effective. Moreover, it suggested that well-planned lessons contributed to increased learner participation and understanding.

Encouraging learner to express their opinions and engage in discussions fostered critical thinking skills. When learners were given the opportunity to analyze and articulate their thoughts, it helped them develop the ability to evaluate different perspectives and form well-reasoned arguments. Additionally, allowing learners to freely express themselves, even in disagreement with the teacher, could boost their confidence. When learners felt that their voices were heard and respected, they were more likely to actively participate in class discussions and express their ideas with confidence.

According to Djigic et al. (2018), the results validated the benefits of the interactionist style of instruction for classroom management. Teachers that adopted an interactionist teaching style promoted cooperation and interaction among students, valued each student's unique personality, acknowledged their initiatives, interests, and needs, and used instructional strategies and resources to engage the entire class in their lessons. They also carefully planned activities that were well-aligned with the objectives of the lesson and put in place procedures to foster positive discipline based on students' self-control and responsibility.

Table 14. Regression Analysis Results between the Teachers' Classroom Management Style and Learners Behavior

Teachers Management Style	t-value	p-value	Remarks
TMS1	-0.299	0.765	Not Significant
TMS2	-0.282	0.778	Not Significant
TMS3	0.106	0.916	Not Significant
TMS4	-0.651	0.516	Not Significant
TMS5	-1.489	0.140	Not Significant
TMS6	1.271	0.206	Not Significant
TMS7	1.304	0.195	Not Significant
TMS8	-0.210	0.834	Not Significant
TMS9	0.357	0.722	Not Significant
TMS10	2.080	0.040	Significant
TMS11	0.680	0.498	Not Significant
TMS12	-1.075	0.285	Not Significant
TMS13	-0.817	0.416	Not Significant
TMS14	2.425	0.017	Significant
TMS15	-0.985	0.327	Not Significant
TMS16	0.499	0.619	Not Significant
TMS17	-1.261	0.210	Not Significant
TMS18	-0.328	0.743	Not Significant
TMS19	1.625	0.107	Not Significant
TMS20	0.693	0.490	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: F=1.716, Significant at 0.01 level, R2=.239

Problem 7: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and classroom management style?

Table 15. Regression Analysis Results Between the Demographic Profile and Classroom Management Style

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	-2.407	0.018	Significant
Civil Status	-2.514	0.013	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	1.697	0.092	Not Significant
Plantilla Position	-1.133	0.260	Not Significant
Length of Service	6.921	0.001	Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: F=12.968, Significant at 0.01 level, R2=.343

Table 15 presents the regression analysis between the demographic profile of the respondents and their classroom management styles. The findings revealed that the age of the respondents had a significant effect on the classroom management style of the respondents as evidenced in the p-value which was 0.018 lower than 0.05 level of significance and t-value of -2.407. It implied that age had something to do with how the respondents managed their classroom, as it was said that experience was the best teacher.

Ismail et al. (2018), revealed that teachers of age 31 to 40 years old, 41 to 50 years old, and 50 years old and above had significantly higher scores in terms of their effectiveness than teachers of age 21 to 30 years old. It could be interpreted that there was a difference between teachers' ages in terms of their effectiveness, which indicated that older teachers were more effective than younger teachers. They were not worried and willing to embrace and prepared to improve the quality of learning and teaching. The reason for their effectiveness in implementing in the classroom settings may be that older teachers were more mature and having had many years of teaching experience made their approaches to teaching more effective.

In like manner, the civil status of the respondents had a significant effect on the classroom management style of the respondents as it

was shown in the table that the p-value was 0.013 which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance. It only meant that being married had something to do with the respondent's classroom management because married respondent had their own experiences of managing their own children at home.

Odanga et al. (2018) came to the conclusion that married and male teachers tried harder in the classroom, endured longer in their profession, and recovered more quickly from setbacks, such as falling short of academic goals. This was a result of the higher planning, inventiveness, resilience, and tenacity of teachers who had high levels of self-efficacy in order to meet goals. Because they show stronger self-efficacy than female and single instructors, respectively, it can be inferred that male and married teachers will work longer and harder to meet goals.

The findings also revealed that there was no significant relationship between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and their classroom management style as the p-value was 0.092 greater than 0.05 level of significance. It meant that whether the respondents had a bachelor's degree or master's degree it did not affect the respondent's classroom management. This was mainly because managing the classroom depended on someone's determination and commitment.

In addition, the plantilla position of the respondent had no significant effect on the classroom management of the respondent as the table showed that its p-value was 0.260 greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The position of a respondent did not affect classroom management in a way that one way of management had nothing to do with our position because managing learners comes from one's experience in life.

On the other hand, length of service of the respondent had a significant effect on the classroom management style with a p-value of 0.001 lower than the 0.05 level of significance. As it was said that length of service was often considered an important factor in determining a teacher's experience and expertise in classroom management. Well-trained and experienced teachers might have better classroom management skills compared to those who were less qualified.

Teachers who had more years of teaching experience were more knowledgeable and teachers with more years of teaching experience had different attitudes, good interactions, class control, and in making decisions. They were more effective, more cautious in taking disciplinary decisions, higher self-efficacies and abilities to manage their students' challenging behaviors. Also, they were in control of their classes and more effective in teaching and classroom management skills (Ismail et al., 2018).

Problem 8: What action plan for classroom management can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Title: "Optimizing Classroom Dynamics: A Comprehensive Action Plan for Strengthening Classroom Management and Enhancing Learner Behavior"

Rationale

This action plan entitled Optimizing Classroom Dynamics: A Comprehensive Action Plan for Strengthening Classroom Management and Enhancing Learner Behavior is designed in a thorough understanding of the multifaceted challenges faced by educators in managing classrooms effectively. It is designed to empower teachers with a diverse set of skills, strategies, and support mechanisms. It creates an optimal learning environment to address the nuanced challenges of classroom management by providing teachers with practical tools, ongoing support, and opportunities for collaboration. It recognizes the dynamic nature of education and aims to empower educators to create environments where learners thrive academically and emotionally.

Action Plan for Enhancing Classroom Management Skills and Promoting Positive Learning Environments: A Comprehensive Strategy for Continuous Improvement

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Resources Needed</i>	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>Success Indicators</i>
Improve teachers' classroom management skills.	Conduct workshops focused on authoritative management styles to reinforce positive practices. Provide training on addressing specific misbehaviors outlined in the study. Introduce effective strategies for maintaining a balanced and engaging classroom environment.	Whole Year Round	Personal MOOE	Teachers	Percentage increase in teachers' knowledge and understanding of authoritative management styles. Number of teachers implementing positive practices learned from workshops. Reduction in disruptive incidents in classrooms.
Ensure emotional well-being without compromising discipline	Emphasize the importance of considering learners' emotions while	Whole Year Round	None	Teachers	Increased awareness among teachers about the importance of considering learners' emotions.

	<p>maintaining a structured environment. Share best practices for managing diverse learner needs within a permissive framework.</p>				<p>Number of teachers implementing permissive frameworks successfully. Improvement in the overall emotional well-being of learners</p>
Develop effective strategies for addressing misbehavior.	<p>Create a guide for teachers on addressing specific misbehaviors identified in the study. Encourage the use of positive reinforcement and motivational activities.</p>	Whole Year Round	None	Teachers	<p>Completion and distribution of the guide on addressing specific misbehaviors. Increase in the use of positive reinforcement and motivational activities by teachers.</p>
Foster collaboration between teachers and parents.	<p>Implement regular communication channels between teachers and parents. Organize workshops for parents on reinforcing positive behavior at home.</p>	Whole Year Round	MOOE	Teachers Parents	<p>Establishment and utilization of regular communication channels between teachers and parents. Number of parents participating in workshops on reinforcing positive behavior at home.</p>
Continuously assess and improve classroom management practices.	<p>Establish a feedback mechanism for teachers to share insights and challenges. Conduct periodic reviews to monitor the effectiveness of implemented strategies.</p>	Whole Year Round	None	School Head Teachers	<p>Existence and utilization of a feedback mechanism for teachers. Positive trends in periodic reviews indicate the effectiveness of implemented strategies. Flexibility and adaptability of teachers in response to challenges and insights.</p>
Enhance future teachers' preparedness for effective classroom management.	<p>Incorporate classroom management modules into pre-service teacher training programs. Collaborate with teacher education institutions to align curricula with practical classroom needs.</p>	Whole Year Round	Personal MOOE	School Heads Teachers	<p>Integration of classroom management modules into pre-service teacher training programs. Alignment of teacher education curricula with practical classroom needs. Feedback from pre-service teachers indicating increased confidence in classroom management.</p>
Facilitate knowledge sharing and peer support.	<p>Establish a platform for teachers to share successful classroom management practices. Encourage mentorship programs for experienced teachers to support newer colleagues.</p>	Whole Year Round	Personal MOOE	School Heads Teachers	<p>Active participation of teachers in the sharing platform. Establishment and effectiveness of mentorship programs. Improvement in overall teacher satisfaction and collaboration.</p>

Ensure ongoing improvement based on feedback and outcomes.	Conduct regular assessments to measure the impact of the action plan. Adjust strategies based on feedback, learner outcomes, and teacher experiences.	Whole Year Round	None	School Heads Teachers	Regular assessments demonstrating positive impacts on teachers and students. Evidence of adjustments made to strategies based on feedback and experiences
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Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated: This study concluded that the majority of teachers fell within the 31-35 age bracket, indicating a concentration of educators in their early to mid-career stages. Married teachers constituted the largest group, potentially drawing from their personal experiences in managing households and influencing classroom management practices. A significant proportion of teachers held Bachelor's Degrees, highlighting the prevalent academic qualification among the respondents. The majority of teachers held the entry-level position of Teacher I, showcasing the hierarchical distribution within the teaching profession. Teachers with 6-10 years of service dominated, suggesting a phase where educators gained experience and refined their classroom management skills.

Teachers predominantly adopted an authoritative management style, emphasizing a genuine concern for learners' learning experiences. While there's occasional use of authoritarian methods, such as maintaining classroom order and discipline, overall, teachers tended to exercise flexibility. Teachers often prioritized learners' emotional well-being, occasionally accommodating requests for hall passes and moments of play during class hours. Teachers sometimes struggled with disciplinary actions, but their approach stemmed from a sincere concern for learners' well-being, fostering a more engaged classroom environment. Teachers have a managerial role, according to Alfie Kohn's Student Directed Learning Theory (2006). It was their responsibility to help students realize that putting in the effort and following rules was worthwhile and might even improve their life. Kohn thought that the most important aspects of the perfect classroom were cooperation and curiosity, both of which could be attained by a strong working relationship. Kohn generally supported putting students at the center of the teaching experience.

Common misbehaviors, such as fighting, disruptive behavior, and attention-seeking, were prevalent. Reasons for misbehavior included peer influence, personal problems, and occasionally seeking attention. Additionally, only specific aspects of classroom management, such as meticulous preparation and fostering an open dialogue with learners, exhibited a significant positive influence on learners' behavior. B.F. Operant Conditioning Theory states that according to Skinner (1960), a person's behavior changes as a result of their reaction to environmental stimuli. Furthermore, all conduct was selected and genetically motivated to fulfill five basic needs—survival, love and belonging, power, freedom, and fun—according to William Glasser's Choice Theory (1998). As a result, the classroom ought to be a location where students' needs are met.

Age and civil status emerged as influential factors in determining classroom management styles. Experience and personal life management experiences may contribute to these variations. Educational attainment, plantilla position, and length of service did not exhibit significant relationships, emphasizing the individualized nature of teaching styles. In essence, this study underscored the dynamic interplay between teachers' demographics, classroom management approaches, and the intricate fabric of learners' behavior. Acknowledging the diverse factors at play was crucial for fostering effective teaching strategies and creating conducive learning environments.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were stipulated below: (1) For district supervisor, design professional development programs that address the distinction of classroom management, with a focus on refining authoritative styles and incorporating flexibility. Tailor these programs to cater to teachers at different career stages. Include training modules that specifically address prioritizing learners' emotional well-being. Equip teachers with tools and strategies to create a supportive and engaging classroom environment that considers the emotional needs of learners. Establish support systems within the district to assist teachers dealing with personal challenges. Recognize the impact of personal life management experiences on teaching styles and provide resources for coping. (2) For school head, develop resources and training materials that assist teachers in handling disciplinary challenges more effectively. Emphasize a balance between maintaining order and fostering a positive learning atmosphere. Encourage collaboration among teachers to share successful classroom management strategies and to ensure that the school environment remains conducive to academic growth. Regular assessments of the school climate and the implementation of initiatives to address any identified areas of improvement can contribute to sustaining a positive educational atmosphere. (3) For teachers, recognize their significant role in shaping learners intellectually and emotionally. Classroom management strategies that promote good positive behavior from the learners and positive relationship between teacher and learners. Teachers are encouraged to be attentive to individual learner's needs, implementing approaches that cater to diverse behavior, learning styles and preferences of the learners. In Addition, teachers are encouraged to advocate for open communication between teachers and learners. Fostering an environment where

learners feel comfortable expressing themselves may contribute positively to classroom management. (4) For future researcher, explore other factors that may influence the classroom management styles of the teachers. While this study provides valuable insights, future research could delve deeper into specific contextual factors that may impact the classroom management of the teachers. Additionally, researchers are encouraged to explore alternative methodologies and perspectives to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between various variables influencing teacher classroom management styles. Continued investigation into the dynamic nature of the school environment, commitment, and parental involvement will contribute to the ongoing improvement of educational practices and policies.

References

- Abalos, J., (2017). Divorce and separation in the Philippines: Trends and correlates. [https:// www. demographic - research.org/volumes/vol36/50/36-50.pdf](https://www.demographic-research.org/volumes/vol36/50/36-50.pdf).
- Abdullah, N. (2020). Comparative study of classroom management strategies employed by public and private school English language teachers: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1259921.pdf>.
- Aliakbari, M. & Bozorgmanesh, B. (2020). Assertive classroom management strategies and students' performance: the case of EFL classroom <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2331186X.2015.1012899>.
- Ariela, S. (2023). How to write a plan of action. <https://www.zippia.com/advice/plan-of-action/>.
- Bacat, F. (2019). Teachers' classroom management style and students academic performance: <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/8355>.
- Barni, D., Russo, C., & Danioni, F. (2018). Teachers' values as predictors of classroom management styles: A relative weight analysis. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6198056/>.
- Best, A.; Tournier, B.; & Chimier, C. (2018). Topical questions on teacher management. Paris: IIEP UNESCO: http://www.iiep.unesco.org/sites/default/files/english_final_topical_questions.pdf.
- Brophy, J. (2018). Classroom management techniques <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0013124586018002005>.
- Chamundeswari, S. (2019). Teacher management styles and their influence on performance and leadership development among students at the secondary level. <http://hrmars.com/admin/pics/1655.pdf>.
- Djigic, G., & Stojiljkovic, S. (2018). Classroom management styles, classroom climate, and school achievement. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/82712560.pdf>.
- Erdogan, M., & Kurt, A. (2020). A review of research on classroom management in Turkey. <https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/277811/1-s2.0S1877042815X0022X/1-s2.0-S1877042815024726/main.pdf>.
- Jen Glantz, J., & Krueger, A. (2023). A good age to marry? An intergenerational model of the influence of timing attitudes on entrance into marriage. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7865042/>
- Glasser, W. (1998). Choice theory. <https://www.theedadvocate.org/understanding-three-key-classroom-management-theories/>.
- Hoff, N. (2020). How to assert teacher authority. <https://corp.smartbrief.com/original/2020/03/how-assert-teacher-authority>.
- Ismail, R, A, M., Abas, Z., & Arshad, R. (2018). Can teachers' age and experience influence teacher effectiveness in HOTS. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324530340_Can_Teachers'_Age_and_Experience_influence_Teacher_Effectiveness_in_HOTS.
- Iqbal, Y. (2018). Classroom management and its impact on the student's academic achievement. Insights from the faculty: <http://rjela.com/6.3.18/144-151%20YASIR%20%20IQBAL.pdf>.
- Johnson, B. (2019). The 5 priorities of classroom management. <https://www.edutopia.org/blog/5-priorities-classroom-management-ben-johnson>
- Johnston, T. (2018). Classroom management. <https://www.palomar.edu/pages/tjohnston2/2018/10/>.
- Kapur, R. (2018). Impact of classroom management on student's behavior https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323834019_Impact_of_Classroom_Management_on_Student's_Behaviors.
- Karakaya, E.G., & Mumin, T. (2018) Social skills, problem behaviors and classroom management in inclusive preschool settings. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1175546.pdf>.
- Kohn, A. (2006). Student directed learning theory. <https://www.theedadvocate.org/understanding-three-key-classroom-management-theories/>.

- Kayikci, K. (2019). The effect of classroom discipline behavior of students <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042809002213#!>.
- Kazak, E., & Koyuncu, V., (2020). Undesired student behaviors, the effects of these behaviors and teachers' coping methods [ender.https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1360747](https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1360747).
- Kini, T., & Podolsky, A. (2018). Does teaching experience increase teacher effectiveness? A review of the research. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED606427.pdf>
- Kirkpatrick, A. (2019). The impact student behavior has on learning. https://nwcommons.nwciowa.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1147&context=education_masters.
- Lewis, R. (2018). Understanding pupil behavior classroom management techniques for teachers. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9780203883914>.
- Lopes, J., Silva, E., Oliveira, C., Sass, D., & Martin, N. (2018). Teacher's classroom management behavior and students' classroom misbehavior: A study with 5th through 9th-grade students. [m_Management_Behavior_and_Students'_Classroom_Misbehavior_n_A_Study_with_5t_through_9th-Grade_Students](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331111111_m_Management_Behavior_and_Students'_Classroom_Misbehavior_n_A_Study_with_5t_through_9th-Grade_Students).
- McAdoo, E.F., (2021) Exploring classroom management styles. <https://www.teachhub.com/classroom-management/2021/05/exploring-classroom-management-styles/>.
- McGinty, J.F. (2020). Classroom management styles and their link to discipline infractions. <https://rdw.rowan.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=https://www.google.com/&httpsredir=1&article=2713&context=etd>.
- Mikami, A.Y., Gregory, A., Allen, J.P., Pianta, R.C., & Lun, J. (2021). Effects of teacher professional development intervention on peer relationships in secondary classrooms. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3379816/>.
- Millapre, M. (2019). Classroom management practices of teacher https://www.academia.edu/29381209/Classroom_Management_Practices_of_Teachers.
- Noman, R. (2023). Classroom management styles: An overview of types. <https://w3ipedia.com/classroom-management-styles/>.
- Obispo, R.T., Magulod, J. C., & Tindowen, D.J. (2021). Teachers' classroom management styles and student-teacher connectedness and anxiety. <file:///C:/Users/Admin/Downloads/3623-14761-2-PB.pdf>.
- Odanga, S.J.O., Aloka, P.J.O., & Raburu, P. (2018). Influence of marital status on teachers' self-efficacy in secondary schools of Kisumu County, Kenya. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283760097_Influence_of_Marital.
- Olmedo, E., & Fernández, M. (2018). Diagnosis of the skills of the master's degree: Case study at the University of Pablo Olavide. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1151058.pdf>.
- Oliveira, H., & Li, Y. (2018). Research on classroom practice. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-12688-3_46.
- Owens, J.S., Holdaway, A.S., Smith, J., Evans, S.W., Himawan, L.K. Coles, E.K., Herrera, E.G., Mixon, C.S., Egan, T. E., & Dawson, A.E. (2018). Journal of emotional and behavioral disorders. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1187699.pdf>.
- Pamela, D. B., Hamilton, G., Lankford, S. L., & Wyckoff, J. (2018). Teacher preparation and student achievement <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED509670.pdf>.
- Parsonson, B. (2020). Evidence-based classroom behavior management strategies. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ976654.pdf>.
- Rahimi, M., & Karkami, F. (2015). The role of teachers' classroom discipline in their teaching effectiveness and students' language learning motivation and achievement: a path method. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1127336.pdf>.
- Shamnadh, M., & Anzari, A. (2019). Misbehavior of school students in classrooms - main causes and effective strategies to manage it. <https://www.ijdsr.org/papers/IJSDR1903053.pdf>.
- Sentillas, E., Limpangog, R., Elorde, M., Estapia, V., Jariolne, D., Acuna, H., Jao, J., & Capampangan, C. (2022). Behavioral management of parents and teachers and the student's performance under the new normal. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358734075_Behavioral_Management_of_Parents_and_Teachers_and_the_Student's_Performance_under_the_new_normal.
- Skinner, B.F. (1960). Operant conditioning. <http://www.instructionaldesign.org/theories/operant-conditioning/>.

Stueber, A.A. (2019). Research-based effective classroom management techniques: A review of the literature. <https://spark.bethel.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1613&context=etd>.

Turanli, A., & Yildirim, A. (2018). A comparative assessment of student classroom behaviors and learning environment in classes of a high control and a low control teacher through student perceptions and class observations. https://www.academia.edu/31425801/A_Comparative_Assessment_of_Classroom_Behaviors_and_Learning_Environment_in_Classes_of_a_High_Control_and_a_Low_Control_Teacher_through_Student_Perceptions_and_Classroom_Observations.

Uibu, K., & Kikas, E. (2022). Authoritative and authoritarian-inconsistent teachers' preferences for teaching methods and instructional goals. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254279393_Authoritative_and_Authoritarian-Inconsistent_Teachers'_Preferences_for_Teaching_Methods_and_Instructional_Goals.

Walker, J. (2019). Authoritative classroom management: How control and nurturance work together. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/60fc/a8fb4a92ee54e0cb49096b2d97fe8d6b0c94.pdf>.

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